

THE IMPORTANCE OF EXERCISES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEG MUSCLES IN WEIGHTLIFTING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6965467>

Abstract: In this thesis, there is enough thought about the proper organization of the methods and exercises used for the development of leg muscles of weightlifters.

Key words: Weightlifting, muscle, leg, strength.

The quadriceps femoris muscle consists of the rectus femoris muscle, which has the shape of a convex roller from the front, the surface of the thigh, the muscle, which is an important part of the lateral broad quadriceps muscle, is attached to the rectus femoris muscle from the outside. During compression, this muscle bends into the direction of the relief roller shape of the outer surface; the vastus internus muscle is located on the inside. This muscle comes almost to the knee, i.e. below the outer head.

The function of the quadriceps muscle consists in the extension of the lower leg, and in addition - in hip flexion. Resting muscles are involved in movements such as squatting.

The second group includes massive muscles, when they approach the popliteal fossa, they are separated, anchored in different places. Biceps femoris, as its name suggests, has two heads. The long head goes down, and then outside, where it meets the short head. Attached to the head of the fibula, it limits the perforated fossa externally. The function of the biceps is to extend the thigh and flex the lower leg, as well as to turn the lower leg outward.

Semitendinosus is a relatively thin muscle. Together with the semimembranous muscle, it forms the internal role of the back of the thigh, the tendons of these two muscles limit the knee joint from the inside hole. Both muscles work flexors in the knee joint and rotators of the lower leg. The muscles in the hip joint are extensors.

Depending on the location, the leg muscles are divided into:

- 1) muscles of the front surface of the thigh (Fig. 1);
- 2) back muscles of the thigh (Fig. 2).

(Fig. 1) Front muscles thigh surface: 1 -

gastrocnemius muscle, 2 – soleus, 3 – long peroneal muscle, 4 – tibialis anterior, 5 – extensor digitorum longus, 6 – broad external muscle, 7 – rectus buttock, 8 – broad internal muscle, 9 – muscle ~ wide retractor fascia, 10 – sartorius, 11 – comb muscle, 12 – long trigger, 13 – soft muscle.

(Fig. 2) Back muscles thigh surface: 1 – gluteus maximus muscles, 2 – biceps femoris, 3 – semi-tendon muscles, 4 – semi-membrane muscles, 5 – smooth muscle, 6 – sole muscles, 7 – calcaneal tendon (Achilles).

The third muscle group is the adductor muscles. The suture muscle separates them from the extensors. The contour of the inner surface of the thigh adductor tender muscles. Contraction of this muscle does not significantly affect the movement of the hip. As a continuation, the inner head of the quadriceps muscle is a long accessory muscle. The scapular muscle fills the space between the sartorius muscle and the long adductor muscle. Adductor muscles do not differ in special relief. If you bring the legs, their contours look good, overcoming the resistance of the central axis of the body. In addition, the members of the considered group of muscles are considered to be involved in flexion and rotation in the hip joint.

The muscles of the lower leg (Fig. 3) can be divided into three groups: muscles of the front surface (extensors), back muscles (flexors) and muscles of the outer surface. The shape of the lower leg is determined by the location of the muscles

near the bones of the lower leg. The anterior tibialis muscle is located near the outer surface of the tibia, and it is slightly shorter than the muscle. Below the anterior tibialis muscle narrows to the raised tendon when working the muscle, the skin near the inside of the ankle. This muscle is felt when lifting the toe up.

(Fig. 3) Leg muscles: 1 – calf muscles, 2 - sole muscles, 3 - long peroneal muscle, 4 – anterior tibialis muscle, 5 – elongated digitorum longus.

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